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**"ANALYSIS OF MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN THE KIDNEYS CAUSED BY
LONG-TERM USE OF DRUGS IN YOUNG CHILDREN."**

Shakhnoza Rakhmonova

University of Business and Science
Lecturer, Department of Natural Sciences
shaxnozrahmonova1980@gmail.com. +998946351333

Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

Tolib Kuldoshevich Botirov

Head of the Angren City Department of the Tashkent
Regional Branch of the Republican Scientific and Practical

Center for Forensic Medical Examination

tolibbotirov1973@gmail.com +998917970220

Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

Normurodov Khurshid Tursunmurodovich

Lecturer, Department of Professional Sciences,
Angren University LLC
khurshid3016966@gmail.com

(97) 301-69-66

Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

Abstract. From a medical point of view, the infant's body should be considered as a being that adapts quickly, but is also susceptible to negative aspects of the process, leading to irreversible changes that do not have time to fully manifest themselves ... Since all anatomical, physiological, biochemical and histological formations of the body from birth to 1 year are not yet fully completed, and even some organ systems They have not fully formed their functions, and external influences can harm the body's resistance. It is the complexity of the kidney structure among the organs, their incomplete formation and the absence of some cells in their histological structure that create the conditions for the development of irreversible changes....

Keywords: kidney tissue, inclusions, newborns. glomeruli, tubules, mesangial cells.

**“ERTA YOSHDAGI BOLALARGA UZOQ QO’LLANILGAN DORI PREPARATLARI
TA’SIRIDA YUZAGA KELGAN BUYRAKDAGI MORFOLOGIK O’ZGARISHLAR
TAHLILI.**

Annotatsiya. Go'daklar organizmi bu tibbiy jihatdan olganda tez moslashuvchanligi shu bilan birga tez beriluvchanligi va jarayonni salbiy tomonlarini yaqqol ko'rsatib berishga ulgurilmasdan qaytmas o'zgarishlarga olib keluvchi mavjudot sifatida ham qaralishi kerak...Yangi tugilgan vaqtdan toki 1 yoshgacha bo'lgan organizmda hali barcha anatomik, fiziologik, bioximik, gistologik shakllanish to'lik yakunlanmaganligi hattoki ba'zi organ tizimi batamom o'z funktsiyasini yo'lga ko'yumaganligi bois ekzogen kiritilgan kiritmalar organizmni qarshiligiga zarar keltirishi mumkin..Aynan a'zolar orasida buyrak tuzilishi murakkabligi ,to'la to'kis shakllanmaganligi va uning gistologik strukturasi ba'zi xujayralarining yo'qligi uning qaytmas o'zgarishlar rivojlanishiga sharoit yaratadi...

Kalit so'zlar: buyrak to'qimasi, kiritmalar. go'daklar, ko'ptokchalar, kanalchalar, mezangial xujayralar..

"АНАЛИЗ МОРФОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ИЗМЕНЕНИЙ В ПОЧКАХ ВЫЗВАННЫХ ДЛИТЕЛЬНЫМ ПРИМЕНЕНИЕМ ЛЕКАРСТВЕННЫХ ПРЕПАРАТОВ У МАЛЕНЬКИХ ДЕТЕЙ."

Аннотация. С медицинской точки зрения, организм младенца следует рассматривать как существо, быстро адаптирующееся, но также восприимчивое к негативным аспектам процесса, приводящим к необратимым изменениям, которые не успевают полностью проявиться... Поскольку все анатомические, физиологические, биохимические и гистологические формирования организма от рождения до 1 года еще не полностью завершены, и даже некоторые системы органов не полностью сформировали свои функции, внешние воздействия могут нанести вред сопротивляемости организма. Именно сложность структуры почек среди органов, их неполное формирование и отсутствие некоторых клеток в их гистологической структуре создают условия для развития необратимых изменений...

Ключевые слова: ткань почек, включения, новорожденных. клубочки, каналы, мезангиальные клетки.

Relevance. In recent years, due to the increasing incidence of many diseases among children, significant progress has been made in studying the structural and functional changes that occur in kidney diseases caused by long-term uncontrolled and irregular use of drugs, as well as the pathogenesis of the disease. At the same time, the increase in diseases of the excretory system, the main part of which is glomerulonephritis and tubular nephritis, which proceed with nephrotic syndrome, and the development of chronic renal failure as a result of the rapid progression of the disease, create the need for early diagnosis of the disease.

According to the data provided in the literature, the survival rate of patients depends on the composition of the drug used and its cumulative ability, the level of clearance, and the degree of formation of the organ tissue of the body. The development of renal pathology in children, based on current research, is attributed to the following reasons:

1. Irregular use of drugs containing aspirin and ibuprofen, which can lead to secondary infection in children. As a result, there is a decrease in blood flow to the kidneys and increased ischemia in the kidney tissue.

2. Continuous use of strong antibiotics, regardless of age, can lead to toxic effects and damage to the renal tubules.

3. The use of drugs with the same composition under different names, but with an inappropriate composition for the child's body, that is, excessively toxic drugs, leads to a shock-like deterioration of renal blood circulation.

As a result of these reasons, acute renal failure in the kidney, i.e., sudden cessation of kidney function, nephrotic syndrome, chronic renal failure, i.e., a decrease in kidney function as a result of repeated use of drugs without understanding the pathology, long-term and irregular use of drugs, cumulative ability to form in the ureters, formation of stones and stones, functional and morphological changes are observed as a result... Functional changes include hematuria, proteinuria, uraturia. observed. During the inspection, the study of the relationship between functional and morphological changes is based.

Research objective: Analytical diagnosis and comparison of morphological changes in children under the influence of long-term use of drugs.

Research method and material. As material from the Republican Scientific and Practical Center for Forensic Medical Examination, a total of 35 autopsy specimens from infants under 1 year of age who were diagnosed with acute renal failure and died between 2025 and 2026 were studied.

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Results: According to the study source, a total of 128 deaths among children were recorded between 2025 and 2026. Of these, 35 were infants under 1 year of age who were clinically diagnosed with acute renal failure and died. Of these 35 infants, 19 were boys and 16 were girls.

Discussion and conclusion: It can be said that when analyzing the total of 35 infants who suffered from acute renal failure and died between 2025 and 2026 by gender, the incidence is higher in girls than in boys, and in percentage terms, boys account for 38.6% and girls for 61.3%.

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